

Analysis of bonding behavior and critical reduction of two-layer strips in clad cold rolling process

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Abstract

In recent years, two-layer metallic sheets have been increasingly used in various industries to create combined functions. Among cladding methods, the cold rolling is most widely used in producing bimetallic sheets. In this research, in order to thoroughly provide guidelines for cold rolling of bimetal strip, an attempt has been made to develop an analytical model based on upper bound method. Also, the bonding strength and critical reduction were calculated using upper bound theorem and the finite element simulation was used for **Al/St** bimetallic strip. Finally, an experimental study was run in order for our model to be verified analytically and numerically. Results show that the bonding strength of strips increases with increasing the total thickness reduction of bimetal strips and because of subsequent occurrence of strips bonding in roll gap, increasing the yield strength of base layer gives rise to critical reduction. Through the study, it becomes clear that the proposed analytical model is applicable for simulating the cold rolling process of the bi-layer strips and is capable to broaden our knowledge in manufacturing and production of bimetal strips and sheets.

Keywords:

Clad rolling; two-layer strip; Analytical model; Upper bound; FEM; Critical reduction

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1. Introduction

Bimetal strips composed of two dissimilar metal layers are being commonly used in a number of fields **such as** aerospace, automobile and electrical industries due to their high electrical conductivity and corrosion resistivity. To avoid isolation between the layers, they are always clad or bonded together using distinct techniques. Many works have been done on how to produce the bimetal strips using cold rolling process in previous years. In bimetal clad rolling process, the variation between the yield stresses of the strip layers results in the different reductions in each layer. Therefore, the deformation study of bimetal strip rolling is more complicated as compared to a single layer strip type. While some work has been performed to study of the process, **further developments are necessary to improve the production** of bimetal strips [1-3].

Afonja and Sansome [1], Pan et al. [2] and Manesh and Taheri [3] have performed experimental works on the mechanism of pressure cold welding applicable in roll bonding. From theoretical viewpoint, Afonja and Sansome [1] based on the slab method, Tzou et al. [4] based on the stream function method, Hwang et al. [5, 6] based on the upper bound theorem, and Lin and Huang [7] based on thermal-elastic-plastic coupled FEM model have proposed their own theoretical models to investigate the deformation behavior of the multilayer sheets in the rolling process. Afonja and Sansome [8] analyzed the sandwich rolling process. This theory was developed to predict the roll separating force to the same level of accuracy as that normally obtained from cold rolling theories, taking into account the thickness of the sheets, the relative yield stresses and the interface friction.

Huang et al. [9] proposed two analytical models to get the stress field of sandwich sheet rolling at the roll gap by using the slab method in order to compare the both rolling characteristics. The neutral point between the roll and sandwich sheet, the rolling pressure distribution, the horizontal stresses in the component layers of the sandwich sheet, the shear stress at the interface of the sandwich sheet, the rolling force and rolling torque could be easily calculated by using these analytical models. Kiuchi et al. [10] proposed mathematical models were based on the extended upper bound theorem and numerical simulations. Through simulations, the flow and deformation feature of each sheet (layer) at roll gap, thickness ratio of each layer in rolled clad or sandwich sheet, rolling force, rolling torque and longitudinal curvature of rolled product were calculated. Recently, Chaudhari and Acoff [11] have modeled cold roll bonding of multi-layered bimetals using the slab

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method. In this work, the effect of anisotropy has been considered and the effects of different process and material variables have been analyzed.

In the current research, by assuming deformation fields as triangles using upper bound theorem, the bonding strength and critical reduction in clad rolling of bi-layer strips have been analyzed in the roll gap. The striking advantage of our analytical model over recent proposed models in the literature is that the effect of neutral point, neglected in those models, has been applied in the velocity field. For verification of the theoretical model and investigation of effects of theoretical simplifications, the finite element simulation of bimetal strip clad rolling was performed. In addition, for verification of theoretical and numerical results, a number of experimental works were performed on the two-layer strip by pure aluminum and mild steel. The results of this research would be beneficial in multi-layer cladding industries to predict the bonding characteristics such as peeling strength, critical reduction, required power, deformation force **etc.**

2. Upper bound theorem on bimetal strip cold rolling

Avitzur and Pachla [12, 13] have made the first attempts about upper bound approach in 1986. They have proposed an upper bound method for deformation of a rigid perfect plastic material in the plane strain condition. In that study, the deformation region is divided into a limited number of rigid triangular sections sliding against each other. They illustrated that any particular work piece shape can be built up by individual sections (rigid zones) characterized by a linear or rotational movement. Although, there is an extensive freedom in defining and combining those zones, one limiting factor is critical. That is the continuity of movement across the boundaries separating the adjacent zones. The shape of those boundaries is obtained by the velocity ratio of the adjacent zones and the direction of movement of those zones. Then, explicit equation is determined to explain the surfaces of shear boundaries between the moving rigid zones, the velocity discontinuities and the shear power losses along those surfaces. Avitzur and Pachla [12, 13] have claimed that the bimetal strip cold rolling process can be considered as a plane strain deformation process where the width of the strips is much greater than its thickness.

In this study the effect of neutral point, which has not been taken care for in previous studies in print is applied in velocity field. The developed velocity field is shown in Fig. 1. After designing each zone and

bounding condition, the shear boundary between the zones is obtained by the velocity of the adjacent zone and the direction of movement in each zone. Finally, the equation of velocity discontinuity surfaces, their amount of velocity discontinuity and shear power losses along these surfaces have been determined using the same equations as used in Avitzur and Pachla [12, 13].

Through the analysis, the following assumptions are applied:

1. The deformation of the strip is plane strain condition.
2. The strip is considered as perfect plastic material.
3. The flatness and bending effects of the rolls are not considered.
4. In the outside of roll gap zone, the velocity distribution is supposed as uniform.
5. A constant friction coefficient by Columbic friction is applied between the strip and roll as well as between the strips at their intimate surfaces.

Fig. 1 : The velocity field developed for bimetal clad rolling Using upper bound method

Fig. 1 illustrates the deformation zones dividing into ten rigid zones. As shown, F point is supposed as first weld point and its distance from origin in X direction is called length of weld. Also B and K are neutral points that their positions in Cartesian System, (x, y), is determined by equation of neutral angle as following

[14]:

$$\sin \gamma = 0.5 \sin(\theta) - (1 - \cos(\theta)) / 2 \quad (1)$$

Where θ is called engage angle and γ is natural angle

In zones (I), (II), (V), (VI) and (VV) the movement is linear with $\alpha=0$ with respect to horizontal direction and the movement in other zones is rotational around roll axes. In this analysis, the first step is the determination of the coordinate of bounding points in each velocity shear boundaries. If the origin of the coordinate axes in Cartesian System, (x, y), is taken as the center of the upper roll, the coordinate of each point in the model can be calculated from Fig. 1 as below:

$$X_A = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$y_A = -R_0 \quad (3)$$

$$y_C = -Y_C \quad (4)$$

$$x_C^2 = R_0^2 - Y_C^2 \quad (5)$$

$$x_D = -X_D \quad (6)$$

$$y_D = -[|y_C| + t_{so}] \quad (7)$$

$$x_E = -X_E \quad (8)$$

$$x_F = -X_F \quad (9)$$

$$y_F = -Y_F = -Y_E - (R_0^2 - X_F^2)^{1/2} - [2t_{sf} / t_f] \{ R_0 + t_f / 2 - (R_0^2 - X_F^2)^{1/2} \} \quad (10)$$

$$x_G = X_G \quad (11)$$

$$y_G = -(R_0 + t_{sf}) \quad (12)$$

$$x_H = -X_H \quad (13)$$

$$x_I = -X_I \quad (14)$$

$$y_H = y_I = -Y_H = -(R_0 + t_f / 2) \quad (15)$$

$$x_J = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$y_I = -(R_0 + t_f / 2) \quad (17)$$

$$y_L = -[|y_C| + t_0] \quad (18)$$

$$x_L^2 = R_0^2 - y_L^2 \quad (19)$$

Hwang and *et al.* [15] have shown that the thickness ratio of strips in the inherent region from welding point (F) to the exit section is constant and equation (10) is obtained from this claim.

2.1. Direction and amount of velocity in each zone

Referring to Fig. 1, the amount and the direction of velocity in every zone can be determined as shown in Table 1. In this table, Γ_i is related to boundaries in deformation area between rigid zones and V_{01} , V_{02} , V'_{01} , V'_{02} and V_f are the initial velocity of clad bimetal, the initial velocity of base metal, the linear velocity of rigid material in zones (V) and (VI) and the final velocity of bimetal strip at the exit of roll gap, respectively. In addition, ω_1 , ω_2 , ω_3 , ω_4 , ω_5 and ω_R are the angular velocity of rigid material in zone (III), (IV), (VII), (VIII), (VIV) and angular velocity of the rolls, respectively.

Table 1
Velocity components for the developed velocity field

Type of velocity	Surface of velocity discontinuity								
	Γ_1	Γ_2	Γ_3	Γ_4	Γ_5	Γ_6	Γ_7	Γ_8	Γ_9
Linear velocity in the rigid zones (V_i)	V_f	V'_{01}	V'_{02}	V'_{02}	V'_{01}	V_{01}	V_{02}	-	-
Input rotational velocities (ω_i)	$-\omega_3$	$-\omega_3$	$-\omega_3$	$-\omega_2$	$-\omega_1$	$-\omega_1$	$-\omega_1$	$-\omega_R$	$-\omega_R$
Output rotational velocities (ω_i)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$-\omega_1$	$-\omega_3$
Angle between linear velocity and X-plane(θ)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-	-
	Γ_{10}	Γ_{11}	Γ_{12}	Γ_{13}	Γ_{14}	Γ_{15}	Γ_{16}	Γ_{17}	-
Linear velocity in the rigid zones (V_i)	-	V'_{01}	V_f	V'_{02}	V'_{02}	V_f	-	-	-
Input rotational velocities (ω_i)	$-\omega_1$	V'_{02}	ω_5	ω_5	ω_4	ω_4	ω_4	ω_5	-
Output rotational velocities (ω_i)	$-\omega_2$	-	-	-	-	-	ω_R	ω_R	-
Angle between linear velocity and X-plane(θ)	-	0	0	0	0	0	-	-	-

2.2. Determination of rotational velocity

Referring to the typical Fig. 2 (a), the angular velocity ω_1 is calculated by the volume constancy law at BEDC region. Other angular velocities ω_2 , ω_3 , ω_4 and ω_5 as well as the linear velocity V'_{01} and V'_{02} are determined as similar by following:

$$V_{01}t_{s0} = \int_{R_0}^{r_E} (\omega_1 r) dr = V_f t_{sf} \quad (20)$$

$$V_f (t_{hf} - t_{sf}) / 2 = \int_{r_D}^{r_I} (\omega_2 r) dr \quad (21)$$

$$V_{01}t_{s0} = V'_{01} \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot [|Y_F| - |Y_B|] = V_f t_{sf} \quad (22)$$

$$V'_{02} [|Y_H| - |Y_E|] = V_f (t_{hf} - t_{sf}) / 2 \quad (23)$$

$$V_f (t_{hf} - t_{sf}) / 2 = \int_{r_G}^{r_H} (\omega_3 r) dr \quad (24)$$

$$V_f (t_{hf} + t_{sf}) / 2 = \int_{R_0}^{r_I} (\omega_4 r) dr = \int_{R_0}^{r_H} (\omega_5 r) dr \quad (25)$$

Where:

$$r_E = \{X_E^2 + Y_E^2\}^{1/2} \quad (26)$$

$$r_D = \{X_D^2 + (Y_C + t_{s0})^2\}^{1/2} \quad (27)$$

$$r_I = \{X_I^2 + (R_0 + (t_{hf} + t_{sf}) / 2)^2\}^{1/2} \quad (28)$$

$$r_G = \{X_G^2 + (R_0 + t_{sf})^2\}^{1/2} \quad (29)$$

$$r_H = \{X_H^2 + (R_0 + (t_{hf} + t_{sf}) / 2)^2\}^{1/2} \quad (30)$$

By substituting Eqns. (26) up to (30) into Eqns. (20) up to (25), the following equations are obtained:

$$\omega_1 = \frac{2V_{01}t_{s0}}{(X_E^2 + Y_E^2 - R_0^2)} = \frac{2V_f t_{sf}}{(X_E^2 + Y_E^2 - R_0^2)} \quad (31)$$

And,

$$\omega_2 = \frac{V_f(t_{hf} - t_{sf})}{X_I^2 + (R_0 + (t_{hf} + t_{sf})/2)^2 - X_D^2 - (Y_C + t_{s0})^2} \quad (32)$$

$$\omega_3 = \frac{V_f(t_{hf} - t_{sf})}{X_H^2 + (R_0 + (t_{hf} + t_{sf})/2)^2 - X_G^2 - (R_0 + t_{sf})^2} \quad (33)$$

$$V'_{01} = \frac{V_f t_{sf}}{(|Y_F| - |Y_B|)} \quad (34)$$

$$V'_{02} = \frac{V(t_{hf} - t_{sf})}{2(R_0 + (t_{hf} + t_{sf})/2 - |Y_E|)} \quad (35)$$

2.3. Velocity ratio of the adjacent zones

Using Eqns. (26) up to (30), the velocity ratio of the adjacent zones can be calculated as shown in Table 2.

Table 2
The adjacent zone velocity ratio of the developed velocity field

Velocity ratio of adjacent zone	Surface of velocity discontinuity								
	Γ_1	Γ_2	Γ_3	Γ_4	Γ_5	Γ_6	Γ_7	Γ_8	Γ_9
$\xi = V/\omega$	$-V_f/\omega_3$	$-V'_{01}/\omega_3$	$-V'_{02}/\omega_3$	$-V'_{02}/\omega_2$	$-V'_{01}/\omega_1$	$-V_{01}/\omega_1$	$-V_{02}/\omega_2$	-	-
$\lambda = \omega_1/\omega_2$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ω_R/ω_1	ω_R/ω_3
Velocity ratio of adjacent zone	Surface of velocity discontinuity								
	Γ_{10}	Γ_{11}	Γ_{12}	Γ_{13}	Γ_{14}	Γ_{15}	Γ_{16}	Γ_{17}	-
$\xi = V/\omega$	-	-	$-V_f/\omega_3$	$-V'_{02}/\omega_5$	$-V'_{02}/\omega_4$	$-V_{02}/\omega_4$	-	-	-
$\lambda = \omega_1/\omega_2$	ω_1/ω_2	-	-	-	-	-	ω_R/ω_4	ω_R/ω_5	-
$\varepsilon = V_1/V_2$	-	V'_{01}/V'_{02}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

2.4. Equation and shape of the surface of shear boundaries

In this model, the equation of the surface of shear boundaries between rigid zones in roll gap can be determined considering the type of movement in adjacent rigid zones. Avitzur and Pachla [12, 13] presented the equation, radius and axis coordinates of these surfaces that have been used in this paper.

Also, for determination of the shear boundaries surface shape, if one or both of adjacent rigid zones have

rotational movement, the surface of velocity between them is cylindrical and if both adjacent rigid zones have a linear motion, the shape of surface of shear boundaries between them is smooth. Therefore, the shear boundaries shape in Fig. 1 is cylindrical. **Fig. 2 (b)** illustrates the schematic of velocity discontinuity surfaces.

Fig. 2 : (a) Schematic models for calculation ω_1 , (b) Illustration of discontinuities surfaces

2.5. Amount of velocity discontinuity

The amount of velocity discontinuity on each surface depends on the type of velocity field in each adjacent rigid zone. Avitzur and Pachla [12, 13] calculated the equation of velocity discontinuity on each surface by which the velocity discontinuity can be derived.

2.6. Determination of velocity discontinuity surface area

For the calculation of the power consumption on each surface of shear boundaries, the area of discontinuity must be determined. Avitzur and Pachla [12, 13] presented the equations to calculate the area of each surface. **By considering** the geometry of shown model in **Fig 1**, **and the unit** width of strip, the area of discontinuity and power consumption equations have been derived.

2.7. Shear power loss on the shear boundaries surface

The power loss on the surface of shear boundaries such as $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \Gamma_3, \Gamma_4, \Gamma_7, \Gamma_{12}$ and Γ_{13} (see Fig. 2 (b)) can be calculated by:

$$W = (\sigma_0 / \sqrt{3}) \Delta V . S_s \quad (36)$$

Where σ_0 is the flow stress of the strip material and ΔV and S_s are the amount of velocity discontinuity and the area of surface of velocity discontinuity, respectively. Also to determine the power loss on surfaces $\Gamma_8, \Gamma_9, \Gamma_{16}, \Gamma_{17}, \Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{11}$ the following equation can be employed:

$$W = (\sigma_0 / \sqrt{3}) . m . \Delta V . S_s \quad (37)$$

Where, m is the constant friction factor at contact surfaces.

3. Calculation of critical reduction and bonding strength

Shear stress in surface Γ_9 consists of three cases:

1. $K' < \tau$. In this state, shear stress on interface of upper roll and clad strip overcomes bonding strength and causes separation of layers as a result of which this state is ignored. This is because as mentioned above, "F" point is assumed as the first weld point.

2. $K' = \tau$. In this case, shear stress is equal to bonding strength. This state is called sliding threshold which based on the conditions mentioned, is used for calculating critical reduction. The following equation, for shear power loss on the surface of velocity discontinuity Γ_9 , is obtained:

$$W = (\sigma_{0s} / \sqrt{3}) \cdot m_1 \cdot \Delta V \cdot S_s \quad (38)$$

Where, S_s is the length of contact Γ_9 . Also, the amount of the lost shear power on the surface of FG is zero.

3. $K' > \tau$. In this case, bonding strength is greater than shear stress. This state can be converted to the following equality:

$$\tau = m_1 \cdot K' \quad (39)$$

Shear power loss on Γ_9 is obtained by following equation:

$$W = K' \cdot m_1 \cdot \Delta V \cdot S_s \quad (40)$$

This state is used for calculating of bonding strength. It is necessary to mention that K' is supposed to be less than shear strength of clad strip ($\sigma_{0s} / \sqrt{3}$).

4. Calculation of total power consumption of rolling

The collective shear power losses on the surface of velocity discontinuities should be evaluated to determine the total power consumption of bimetal strip cold rolling. So, the following relation calculates the total power of plastic deformation:

$$J = W_{\Gamma_1} + W_{\Gamma_2} + W_{\Gamma_3} + \dots + W_{\Gamma_{17}} \quad (41)$$

The upper bound value for power consumption presented by Eq. (41) is a function of independent process parameters, namely σ_{0s} , σ_{0h} , R_0 , t_{s0} , t_{h0} , t_{sf} , t_{hf} , V_f , m_1 , m_2 and K' and pseudo-independent parameters such as X_C , X_D , X_E , X_F , X_H and X_I .

The optimization of Eq. (41) can be performed with respect to these parameters numerically to supply the unique solution by the upper bound method. Rao [16] presented simplex numerical method for the

optimization. Consequently, in this work using this method, the total power consumption of bimetal strip cold rolling was calculated by the upper bound theory of Eq. (41) with respect to the geometrical parameters such as X_C , X_D , X_E , X_F , X_H , X_b , t_{sf} , V_f and K' has been optimized. By substituting the optimal values of these parameters in Eq. (41) the minimum energy required for deformation is calculated. Also, to calculate critical reduction, in addition to above mentioned parameters, the roll gap replaces K' as an independent process parameter in the simplex numerical method.

5. Numerical simulation

The finite element (FE) simulations were conducted on the available commercial explicit/FEM software to verify the analytical model and study the effects of upper bond method assumptions on the obtained results.

Fig. 3 shows the model geometry and meshed bimetal strips used in FE simulation. The strips composing the laminates with the entry total thickness of 1.1mm used in the FE model are St12 with 1.5mm-thick and **AL1100** with 0.7mm-thick strips. The strip was meshed by 2D plane strain, linear, four-noded CPE4R elements. The strip model contained 6000 elements.

Fig. 3 : A schematic view of meshed geometry of FE model

In this model, the rolls were modeled as rigid bodies with roll radius equal to $R_0 = 70$ mm. The rolls were rotated by constant angular velocity of $\omega = 2$ rad/s about their axes. No lateral transitions were assumed for the rolls in the analyses. The gap between two rollers was considered fix without external loading equal to %25 up to %55. To avoid complexity, the diffusion phenomenon in the interface of two strips during rolling was not considered.

The elastic-plastic model with Hollomon strain hardening was used to describe the behavior of both steel (St12) and aluminum (**Al1100**) (i.e., $\bar{\sigma} = K\bar{\epsilon}^n$, where $\bar{\sigma}$ was equivalent stress, the $\bar{\epsilon}$ equivalent strain, K and n the material constants). The mechanical properties of both materials are given in **Table 3**.

Coulomb and sticking friction equation were used to describe the friction behavior between the rollers and sheets, i.e.,

$$\tau = \min(\mu P, mK) \quad (41)$$

Coulomb friction coefficients of 0.1 and 0.12 in oily condition and 0.18 and 0.22 in dry condition were considered for aluminum and steel contact surfaces with rigid rollers, respectively [17]. For verification of theoretical study, the results of rolling force and reduction of each layer were extracted from FE simulations. In the developed FE model, the effect of cladding and bonding of layers during rolling has been ignored.

6. Experimental

6.1. Specimen preparation

To verify the theoretical analysis developed in the present research, a series of tests were executed. These tests were conducted on 0.7-mm-thick aluminum Al1100 and 1.5-mm-thick mild steel strips. Before clad rolling, strips were degreased by swabbing with acetone and dried in the air. Then, the interface surface of the strips was scratch brushed for proper bonding purpose.

6.2. Rolling process

After surface preparation, the specimens containing **Al-1100** and mild steels (St12, St13) were rolled simultaneously using different thickness reductions without lubrication (dry condition). The rolling forces at

different reduction of thickness were measured using the digital force system of the rolling mill.

For calculation of theoretical rolling force, the following equation was used in this research [18]:

$$F = \frac{J.R_0}{L.U_0} \quad (42)$$

$$L = \sqrt{R_0.t_i.r} \quad (43)$$

where F , J , L , R_0 , t_i , U_0 , and r are the rolling force, the rolling power determined by the upper bound method, the length of contact, the radius of roll, the initial thickness of bimetal, the linear velocity of roll and the reduction of thickness, respectively. In this investigation, the width of sample was greater than six times of its thickness to reach the plane strain condition. Moreover, in this research, the mean effective stress for the strain hardening materials was determined approximately by the following equation [19]:

$$\bar{\sigma}_0 = \frac{\int_0^{\bar{\varepsilon}_t} \bar{\sigma} d\bar{\varepsilon}}{\bar{\varepsilon}_t}, \quad \bar{\sigma} = K \bar{\varepsilon}^n \quad (44)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_t = (2/\sqrt{3}).\ln \frac{1}{1-r} \quad (45)$$

Where $\bar{\varepsilon}$, is the average total effective strain and r is the reduction of thickness.

6.3. Peeling test

The amount of the bounding strength of the clad metal sheets was measured by the peeling test according to ASTM-D903-93. In peeling test the breaking off force is measured as follows:

$$\text{Average Peel Strength} = \frac{\text{Average Load}}{\text{Bond Width}} \quad (46)$$

The peeling test was performed using an Instron tensile testing machine with 1 KN load cell. The mean peeling force was measured by a clamping configuration shown in **Fig. 4**. A crosshead speed of 20 mm/min was in the tests.

Fig. 4 : Experimental set-up of the peeling test

7. Results and discussion

7.1. Stress–strain curves

The determination of the stress–strain curves for mild steel and pure aluminum was based on the standard plane strain compression test. A stress-strain relation as power law hardening rule, $\bar{\sigma} = K\bar{\epsilon}^n$ fitted to the experimental data for each material given in Table 3:

Table 3
Mechanical properties of bimetal strip components

Material	Thickness, t (mm)	Young's Modulus, Y_s (MPa)	Strain hardening coeff., K (MPa)	Strain hardening exponent, n
Pure aluminum (Al 1100)	0.70	47	212	0.21
Mild steel (St12)	1.5	210	552	0.40

7.2. Rolling power and rolling force

The effect of reduction of thickness on the rolling power required for rolling the Al1100/mild steel bimetal is shown in **Fig. 5**. This figure illustrates that when the total reduction of thickness and friction factor m_1 between the roll and strips increase, the rolling power increases as well. In this figure, the theoretical curves

of rolling power against reduction of thickness are illustrated for two different friction factors (m_1) between rolls and strips. Comparing the theoretical and experimental results of rolling power for the bimetal strips, a friction factor between strips and roll was calculated to be equal to 0.6.

Fig. 5 : Effect of reduction on rolling power of Al 1100/Mild Steel

Using Eqns. (42) and (43), the theoretical rolling force was determined by the rolling power predicted by the presented mathematical model. **Fig. 6** shows that the rolling force of the bimetal strip is increased with the total reduction of thickness. Furthermore, the rolling forces are increased with increasing the friction factor at a constant reduction of thickness of composite sheet. In **Figs. 5** and **6**, with **due** attention to the digressing and scratch brushing of the intimate surfaces of sheets before rolling, it can be assumed that the value of m_2 is equal to 1.

Fig. 6 : Effect of reduction on rolling force of Al 1100/Mild Steel

7.3. Bonding strength, thickness reduction and critical reduction

Considering Fig. 7, the reduction of thickness of each layer of the bimetal strip (Al 1100/mild steel) is dissimilar at a constant reduction of thickness of composite sheet **due to the difference in yield stress of the layers in bimetal strip**. Also, at constant thickness reduction of the bimetal strip, the reduction of the softer metal (Al 1100) is greater than the harder metal (mild steel). In this figure, the theoretical curve has been plotted with considering the sticking friction condition ($m_2=1$). Regarding this figure, a good agreement is observed between theoretical results and experimental works of the rolling experiments. In the FE model, because of neglecting the bonding of the layers, the layers do not extrude.

Fig. 7 : Reduction of each layer versus reduction of composite sheet

Fig. 8(a, b) shows the contours of equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) and plastic strain (PE) in thickness direction during cold rolling simulation. According to these contours, the maximum PEEQ is observed in **Al** layer that conforms to more reduction of **Al** layer in a specific total reduction similar to theoretical study. Also, the negative magnitude of PE in **Fig. 8(b)** illustrated this phenomenon in other words.

Fig. 8 : Counters of (a) equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ), (b) thickness plastic strain (PE) in bimetal strip rolling

Eizadjou and *et al.* [20] showed the average peel strength of bimetal strip increases with thickness reduction. **Fig. 9** illustrates the reality of this claim. This is due to the increase in the thickness reduction of each layer as well as rolling force with total thickness reduction as described in **Figs. 6** and **7**. By increasing the bimetal thickness reduction the surface ratio for the outer and inner layer changes and, as a result, a higher mean contact pressure at the interface between the strips was attained. Also, in this figure, a good agreement was observed between theoretical results and experimental works of the rolling experiments.

Fig. 9 : Effect of reduction on average peeling strength of bimetal strip

Bay [21, 22] proved that the bond strength is affected by factors including solid and surface physics, such as surface cleanness and diffusion, also Hwang and *et al.* [15] showed in addition to the mentioned parameters, bonding strength is affected by mechanical factors such as thickness reduction and rolling pressure. The results of critical reduction in the analytical and experimental works for two types of mild steel are shown in Table 4.

Table 4
The results of critical reduction in the analytical and experimental works

Components	Experimental			Analytical		
	t_{Al}^* (mm)	t_{St}^* (mm)	Critical Reduction (%)	t_{Al}^* (mm)	t_{St}^* (mm)	Critical Reduction (%)
St13/Al 1100	0.42	1.45	15	0.44	1.34	19
St12/Al 1100	0.49	1.44	12	0.52	1.35	15

*Thickness, after rolling

The critical reduction is affected by factors including solid and surface physics, such as surface cleanness and the substance of layers. Since the yield strength of St13 is more than St12, the extrusion of layers and bonding in the rolls gap causes the increase of the critical reduction.

8. Conclusion

In this research, cold rolling process of bimetal strip was studied by upper bound theorem and finite element simulation. To verify the theoretical and numerical models, an experimental setup was designed. The experimental work was conducted using Al 1100/mild steel strips. A good agreement among the theoretical, numerical and experimental results was observed. The effect of thickness reduction on process parameters such as rolling force, reduction of each layer and peeling strength was studied. Also, a comparison between the experimental and theoretical results on the critical reduction was carried out. The following are the results obtained:

(1) **The** good agreement between the analytical and experimental results **shows that** the bonding strength and critical thickness reduction are predictable by upper bound theorem.

(2) Increase in the reduction of thickness gives rise to the bonding strength of bimetal strips. In this state, the bond strength is influenced by mechanical factors such as rolling pressure and thickness reduction.

(3) Increase in the yield strength of base layer increases the critical reduction because of occurrence **of** the bonding phenomenon between strips in the roll gap.

(4) Due to the difference in yield stress of the layers in bimetal cold rolling, the thickness reductions of the layers are dissimilar, so, at constant thickness reduction of the bimetal strip, the reduction of the softer metal (**Al 1100**) is greater than the harder metal (Mild Steel). Being a good agreement among theoretical, numerical and experimental results, the prediction of final thickness of each layer is possible at the end of rolling process.

(5) According to the results, the presented mathematical model is capable of successfully predicting the bimetal cold rolling process and is efficient to give a better insight into the manufacturing and production of bimetal sheets and strips.

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Nomenclature

t_i (mm)	initial thickness of bimetal strips	n	strain hardening exponent
t_f (mm)	final thickness of bimetal strips	Γ_i	surface of velocity discontinuity
t_0 (mm)	initial thickness of composite	R_0 (mm)	radius of roll
t_{s0} (mm)	initial thickness of clad layer	R_i (mm)	radius of cylindrical surface of velocity discontinuity
t_{h0} (mm)	initial thickness of base layer	ξ_i and λ_i	velocity ratio in the rigid zones
t_{sf} (mm)	final thickness of clad layer	ΔV_i	amount of velocity discontinuity on each surface of velocity discontinuity
t_{hf} (mm)	final thickness of base layer	(mm/s)	
V_{01} (mm/s)	initial velocity of clad layer	W_i	shear power of the surface of velocity discontinuity
V_{02} (mm/s)	initial velocity of base layer	J^*	total shear power
V_f (mm/s)	final velocity of bimetal strip	m_1	friction factor between roll and strips
V (mm/s)	linear velocity of roll	m_2	constant friction factor between layers
V'_{01}, V'_{02}	linear velocity in (V) and (VI) regions	σ_{0s} (MPa)	yield stress of clad layer (outer layer)
(mm/s)		σ_{0h} (MPa)	yield stress of base layer (inner layer)
ω_R	rotational velocity of roll	T (MPa)	shear stress
ω_i	rotational velocity of each rigid zone	K' (MPa)	bonding strength between of two layer
O_i	center of cylindrical surface of velocity discontinuity		

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References

- 1 **A. A. Afonja**, and **D. R. Sansome**, An experimental investigation of the sandwich rolling of thin hard sheets. Proc. of the 13th Int. MTDR Conf., 1972, pp.12-18.
- 2 **D. Pan**, **K. Gao**, and **J. Yu**, Cold roll bonding of bimetallic sheets and strips, Mater. sci. & tech., 5, 1989, pp. 934-939.
- 3 **H. D. Manesh** and **A. K. Taheri**, A Study of mechanisms of cold roll welding of aluminum alloy to steel strip, Mater. sci. & tech., 20, 2004, pp. 1064–1068.
- 4 **G. Y. Tzou**, **K. I. Lee**, **H. R. Jian** and **J. C. Lion**, Analysis of the cold and hot bond rolling of clad sheet, Metal Forming, 2000, pp. 315-321.
- 5 **Y. M. Hwang**, **T. H. Chen** and **H. S. Hsu**, Analysis of asymmetrical clad sheet rolling by stream function method, Int. J. Mech. Sci., 38, 1996a, pp. 443-460.
- 6 **Y. M. Hwang**, **H. H. Hsu** and **H. J. Lee**, Analysis of plastic instability during sandwich sheet rolling, Int. J. Mach. Tools Manuf., 36 (1), 1996b, pp. 47-62.
- 7 **Z. C. Lin** and **T. G. Huang**, Different degree of reduction and sliding phenomenon study for three-dimensional hot rolling with sandwich flat strip, Int. J. Mech. Sci., 42, 2000, pp. 1983-2012.
- 8 **A. A. Afonja** and **D. H. Sansome**, A theoretical analysis of the sandwich rolling process, Int. J. Mech. Sci. 15, pp. 1-14, 1973.
- 9 **M. N. Huang**, **G. Y. Tzou** and **S. W. Syu**, Investigation on comparisons between two analytical models of sandwich sheet rolling bonded before rolling, J. of Mat. Proc. Tech., 140, 2003, pp. 598-603.
- 10 **M. Kiuchi**, **K. Shintani** and **Y. M. Hwang**, Mathematical simulation of cold sheet rolling and sandwich sheet rolling, Ann. CIRP 41, 1992, pp. 289-292.
- 11 **G. P. Chaudhari**, and **V. Acoff**, Cold roll bonding of multi-layered bi-metal laminate composites, Sci. and Tech. 69, 2009, pp. 1667-1675.
- 12 **B. Avitzur** and **W. Pachla**, The upper bound approach to plane strain problems using linear and rotational velocity fields-part I: Basic concepts, J. of Eng. Ind., 108, 1986a, pp. 295-306.
- 13 **B. Avitzur** and **W. Pachla**, The upper bound approach to plane strain problems using linear and rotational velocity fields-part II: Application, J. Eng. Ind., 108, 1986b, pp.307-316,

Pre-print of: M. Maleki, S. Bagherzadeh, B. Mollaei-Darjani & [Karen Abrinia](#) (2013). Analysis of bonding behavior and critical reduction of two-layer strips in clad cold rolling process. Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance. DOI: [10.1007/s11665-012-0342-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-012-0342-9)

14 Tselikov, A. *Stress and Strain in Metal Rolling*. Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1967.

15 Hwang, Y.M., Hsu, H.H. and Hwang, Y.L. Analytical and experimental study on bonding behavior at the roll gap during complex rolling of sandwich sheets. Int. J. of Mech. Sci. 42, pp. 2417-2437, 2000.

16 Rao, S.S. Optimization: *Theory and Application*, second edition, Wiley Eastern Limited, pp. 292, 1984.

17 Chen, L., Yang, J.C., Zhang, L.W. and Yuan, S.Y. Finite element simulation and model optimization of blankholder gap and shell element type in the stamping of a washing-trough. J. Mater. Proc. Tech. 182, pp.637–643, 2007.

18 Hwang, Y.M. and Kiuchi, M. Analysis of asymmetrical complex rolling of multi-layer sheet by upper bound method. J. Chinese Soc. Mech. Engrs. 13 (1), pp. 33-45, 1992.

19 Dieter, G.E. *Mechanical Metallurgy*, second edition, Mc-Graw Hill Inc., pp. 548, 1976.

20 Eizadjou, M., Manesh H.D. and Janghorban, K. Investigation of roll bonding between aluminum alloy strips. Int. J. Mat. and Des 29, pp. 909-913, 2008.

21 Bay, N. Cold welding: Part I, characteristic, bonding mechanisms and bond strength. Metal Construct., pp.369-372, 1986a.

22 Bay, N. Cold welding: Part II, process variants and application. Metal Construct., pp.486-490, 1986b.

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